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PERIODIC WAKE IMPINGEMENT AND STALL DRIVING LOSS IN AXIAL COMPRESSORS

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ABSTRACT

Axial compressors are used in power generation and aircraft engines. In compressor design, three dimensional blading is already common. Since the flow structure in axial compressors is inherently unsteady, it is of interest to study salient features of axial compressor flows by time-resolved approaches. This paper shows how flow separation can be affected by the periodic interaction between the wake of a preceding blade row and the vane boundary layer, and how stall inception in a highly loaded axial compressor develops.

Laminar flow separation on a flat plate under periodic wake impingement is studied in the closed-loop low-speed wind tunnel of the University of Leicester. Static pressure measurements by flush-mounted taps and microphones visualize the flow separation on the flat plate. These measurements also show that the naturally occurring transitional flow separations can be calmed by periodic forcing the inflow using small gusts produced by leading-edge mounted synthetic jets.

The unsteady flow developed during stall inception in the NASA rotor 37 is investigated by time-dependent RANS simulations. An improvement in the rotor stall margin is obtained by a new casing treatment concept, based on a recirculation channel in the casing. The numerical simulations predict that the recirculation channel extends the rotor operating range significantly without any penalty to the rotor adiabatic efficiency over the rotor operating line.

INTRODUCTION

Improvements in material and manufacturing technology over the last four decades have produced a drive to reducing the number of blades in axial turbomachine blade rows [1]. Reducing the blade count offers attractive savings in the manufacturing cost, maintenance cost, and in the weight of axial turbomachines. By reducing the blade count in both stators and rotors for a given shaft speed, the

frequency by which trailing edge wakes shed by the upstream blade row interact with the downstream blade row reduces. Intuitively, this should lead to a monotonic decrease in the stage loss with decreasing blade count, a trend that however was not confirmed in tests on blading under a strong adverse streamwise pressure gradient.

The disturbances generated by on-coming wakes play a vital role in preserving the efficiency and the integrity of compressors. This is manifest in both the midspan locations and also at locations close to the hub or to the casing. This discussion is limited to midspan locations, where wake disturbances affect the quasi-two dimensional flow. The engines of contemporary aircraft are particularly susceptible to loss of efficiency and stall margin, therefore the present discussion is relevant to those phenomena.

However the discussion wishes to go beyond a parametric study on aggregate stage performance parameters, such as stage efficiency and stall margin, which are nonetheless of real practical importance. There is a need to address the fundamental aerodynamic background of the interaction processes. It will be seen that, not only do the somewhat obvious mixing and entropy generation processes of turbulence affect the efficiency and stall margin, but the low turbulence levels prevailing under the low Reynolds levels of high altitude also have a major impact. It will be seen that the effect of this low Reynolds number turbulence is not always negative. However, this is a subtle effect and is easily masked at higher Reynolds numbers, where mixing loss and other mechanisms are more dominant. It will be shown that the blade boundary layers can be affected by the state of the blade wake/boundary interactions and whether the transition is a natural one or whether the blade design of the boundary layer is conducive to a different transition process.

Another area in which unsteady aerodynamic effects play a significant role in determining the performance of axial compressor is stall and surge. Stall inception of axial

compressor has attracted extensive research interest, due to its wide-reaching limiting effect on the operation of airborne and land-based turbomachines, including aircraft turbofan engines, gas cycles for power generation, air conditioning, and refrigeration systems.

The early investigations into the rotating stall inception mechanism were mainly conducted by rig experiments. Since the flow structure during the stall inception is particularly complicated, it is difficult to fully understand this phenomenon by experimental measurements only. To support the analysis of this transient flow feature, CFD has been widely used in recent years. Cameron et al. [2] conducted three-dimensional time-resolved Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations on a transonic axial compressor stage. Their simulations predicted that the relocation of the interface between the inflow to the blade row and the reversed flow from the rotor tip clearance is one of the main drivers leading to the rotating stall in axial compressors. They also visualized the transient development of rotating stall by multi-passage time-dependent CFD analysis.

Mitigating the onset of stall is among the design requirements of axial compressors. Gallimore et al. [3] evaluated the performance of a multistage axial compressor with aerofoil sweep and dihedral. They evaluated the effect of sweep and dihedral blading by a numerical approach and rig experiments. Their work contributed to enhancing the stability of a production engine, the TREN 500 turbofan. This is reported as the first time sweep and dihedral blading has been employed successfully on a multi-stage engine compressor. Currently, three-dimensional blading is becoming a popular design in production engines.

Another technique for improving in the stability of axial compressors is casing treatment. This is a passive approach that may attract a lower compressor weight penalty compared to active flow control approaches. Although many contributions to the performance evaluation of casing treatments have been reported in literature [4-6], this design approach is not widely used compared to three-dimensional blading.

Gourdain and Leboeuf [4] investigated the flow structure in a single stage axial compressor with non-axisymmetric slots by a numerical approach. Their time-resolved numerical simulations showed that the axial slots with a curved roof extend the compressor stable operating range but with a penalty in the compressor efficiency. They also examined the effect of the longitudinal groove treatment applied to the rotor blade tip surface.

Circumferential grooves tend to give lower gains in stall margin but they are easier to manufacture than non-axisymmetric grooves. Houghton and Day [5] evaluated the effect of the location and of the depth of a square groove casing treatment on the performance of a subsonic compressor stage. Their experimental parametric study showed that a deeper groove provides larger stall margin improvement but it also gives a larger decrease in the adiabatic efficiency.

The recirculating type casing treatment is an advanced design strategy that could be more effective in improving the stability of axial compressors than conventional casing

treatments. Hathaway [6] evaluated the performance of an axial flow compressor rotor with flow recirculation by solving numerically the one-dimensional mass balance equations between the channel inlet and the channel outlet. His simulation highlighted that the casing flow recirculation has the positive effect of extending the compressor operating range without any compressor efficiency penalty. A fundamental study on the recirculating type casing treatment was conducted by Hathaway [6], but a more comprehensive concept evaluation is required to mature this design approach to a stage that can be used, with confidence, in the design process of an operational axial compressor.

This paper aims to provide insight into the working principle of the recirculation-type casing treatment and into its performance over a representative operating envelope, for a highly loaded axial rotor. By numerical modelling, this paper gives a clear insight of the near-casing flow changes from the casing treatment that lead to a delay in the rotor tip stall onset.

WAKE DISTURBANCES ON A COMPRESSOR BLADE

Flow separation on a flat plate by periodic wake impingement

In this section of this paper, the transition and separation phenomena occurring in axial flow compressors are simulated on a larger scale to provide further evidence on the similarities between turbomachinery and wind tunnel flows. This experimental approach was elected as it provides the means for observing the interaction between a modelled blade wake and a downstream boundary layer uncluttered from the secondary flows that typically develop through a turbomachinery stage. It also enabled good access to the target flow by conventional measurement techniques.

The experiments were performed on a flat plate (Fig. 1) in the $0.84 \text{ m} \times 1.15 \text{ m}$ working section of the University of Leicester closed-loop low-speed research wind tunnel (the Charles Wilson wind tunnel). A flat plate carried a long laminar separation bubble, caused by a strong adverse pressure gradient. The Reynolds number, based on the plate length of 2.41 m, was 1.4×10^6 . During the tests, the wind tunnel velocity was set to this target Reynolds number. The free stream turbulence level was less than 0.2%.

The roof of the test section was contoured to provide the desired strong adverse pressure gradient, providing self-similar conditions with a Hartree [7] β parameter of -0.221 between 0.4 m and 0.7 m streamwise from the flat plate leading edge ($x = 0$). The converging section of the wind tunnel test section included the first 0.15 m of the flat plate, terminating at the throat.

Figure 2 shows the resulting time-averaged static pressure distribution along the flat plate. This was measured by flush-mounted static pressure taps along the flat plate centreline. Two distributions are shown, one for which the boundary layer on the flat plate is fully attached, and one for which the laminar boundary layer is separated and forms a laminar separation bubble. The streamwise static pressure distribution in Fig. 2 is shown to cover a modest pressure coefficient (C_p) range, over the flat plate.

Fig. 1. Flat plate installation with flat plate, fairing, hot wire traverse, and upstream wake generator.

Fig. 2. Pressure coefficient distribution along the flat plate.

The presence of a laminar separation bubble over the flat plate is shown in Fig. 2 to produce a subtle but measurable change in the static pressure streamwise distribution, as labelled in the figure.

Over the flat plate, through the streamwise range shown in Fig. 2, the flow evolves from a laminar state to a turbulent flow state. This flow evolution is depicted schematically in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b). Tollmien-Schlichting (T-S) waves grow over the upstream portion of the flat plate. In the case of continuous breakdown, shown schematically in Fig. 3(a), each T-S wave evolves into an individual turbulent flow generation event over the transition length L_T .

Alternatively, Fig. 3(b) depicts a schematic in which T-S waves break down in sets. In this case, multiple T-S waves participate to the generation turbulent flow. The T-S wave breakdown through the centre of Fig. 3(b) is dominated by larger turbulent structures of less well-ordered behaviour. Each set is terminated by a calmed region. The turbulence in these calmed regions tends to begin earlier and end later than in the equivalent turbulent wedge. An understanding of this fundamental behaviour is essential for the prediction of breakdown by sets and by vigorous wave activity.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Schematic of transition based on methods of breakdown (a) by continuous breakdown and (b) by sets.

Fig. 4. Static pressure taps (left) and microphone array (right) along the flat plate centreline.

Pressure measurements by a microphone array inside the flat plate

The modest difference in static pressure distribution with and without a laminar separation bubble shown in Fig. 2 prompted to find a complementary experimental technique to identify and locate flow separation at the separated flow test conditions. The presence of the laminar separation bubble was further confirmed by instrumenting the flat plate by a streamwise array of microphones, mounted inside the flat plate casing, as shown in Fig. 4. 28 microphones were installed along the flat plate centreline and cabled through the flat plate trailing edge. The microphones were numbered progressively from the flat plate leading edge towards the flat plate trailing edge.

Figure 5 shows a sample of the time traces acquired by the 28 microphones. The microphone number is reported on the ordinate. Microphone 16 is the closest one to the flat plate leading edge among the set in Fig. 5. The background behaviour is of relatively high free stream turbulence. This is shown by relatively low amplitude and high frequency oscillations over the range $0 \leq t \leq 0.15$ seconds. The flow is subsequently perturbed by an oncoming large structure. This is dominant and it affects the smaller Tollmien Schlichting structures, which are suppressed. This is shown in Fig. 5 by the suppression of high frequency oscillations over the range $0.25 \text{ seconds} \leq t \leq 0.35 \text{ seconds}$. A temporary region of low turbulence, or calmed flow, develops, which is referred to as the calmed region. The calmed region is thus seen to have a significant influence in moderating high frequency free stream turbulence levels.

Fig. 5. Synchronous microphone time traces showing high free stream turbulence and the calmed region.

Figure 6 shows a space-time diagram of the recorded pressure from the microphones, using levels of grey. Upstream of $x = 0.6 \text{ m}$, the pressure is streamwise uniform and the flow is relatively quiet, as indicated by the mid-grey tone. Between $x = 0.6 \text{ m}$ and $x = 0.7 \text{ m}$, noticeable pressure fluctuations are detected, with a positive phase speed. These fluctuations are likely to be the result of propagating flow instabilities generated on the rearward facing surface of the laminar separation bubble. Whereas microphones are used in this experiment, the nature of this pressure fluctuation is hydrodynamic, rather than acoustic, as shown by the slope of its signature on the space-time diagram of Fig. 6. The consistent inclination of the striations in the space-time plot points to streamwise developing Tollmien Schlichting (T-S) waves. The latter showed a tendency for the oscillatory motion to break down in sets, in the same way that sketched in Fig. 3(b). This was an early indication of the turbulent spot and of the attached calmed region.

The flat plate was then equipped with three synthetic jets close to the flat plate leading edge. Fig. 7 shows corresponding measurements to the ones reported in Fig. 6 but with the synthetic jets in operation.

Actuating the synthetic jets induced turbulent spots that propagated downstream of the flat plate, as indicated by the positive slope of the striations in the space-time diagram of Fig. 7, spanning from left to right in this figure.

Fig. 6. Results from the microphone array.

What is interesting to notice, and relevant to turbomachinery flows, is that the intermittent operation of the synthetic jets caused regions of relatively unperturbed flow between duty cycles. These temporary regions of quiet flow are shown in Fig. 7 by a uniform grey tone level in between patches of striations and are labelled as “Calmed region”.

Fig. 7. Results from the microphone array showing turbulent spots and the calmed region.

ANALYSIS OF TIP STALL INCEPTION IN A HIGHLY LOADED AXIAL COMPRESSOR

Numerical modelling

The rotor passage geometry of the NASA rotor 37 [8-10] is used as the benchmark test case. Table 1 lists the main design parameters of the NASA rotor 37. The aerodynamic performance of the NASA rotor 37 was measured at the NASA Glenn research center (formerly known as the NASA Lewis research center). Since this rotor was designed to have fairly high total pressure ratio of 2.1, this compressor rotor has been used by many researchers as the test case for evaluating new design techniques for turbomachines that require compact and highly loaded compressors.

Figure 8(a) gives the overview of the computational domain and mesh through one passage of the NASA rotor 37. The computational mesh is generated by ANSYS ICEM CFD. This single passage computational domain corresponds to $1/36^{\text{th}}$ of the rotor full annulus. To observe the flow features leading to the rotating stall in the axial compressor, a multi-passage computational mesh is generated by replicating the one blade-to-blade passage mesh shown in Fig. 8(a) 12 times in the circumferential direction. In Fig. 8(a), the mesh is visualized coarsened by a factor of two in each spatial direction, for image rendering purposes.

(a) Structured mesh for the one blade-to-blade passage simulation.

(b) Overview of the recirculation channel.

Fig. 8. NASA rotor 37 passage computational mesh and overview of the recirculation channel applied over the NASA rotor 37.

The mesh dependence of the predictions was assessed on the basis of Richardson's extrapolation [11]. To estimate the error caused by the spatial discretization on the flow predictions, three meshes are used with a constant refinement ratio of 2.0. These are a coarse mesh of 0.7 million nodes (mesh A), a mesh of intermediate spatial refinement of 1.5 million nodes (mesh B), and a fine mesh of 3.1 million nodes (mesh C). The grid convergence index (GCI) is calculated based on the adiabatic efficiency of the rotor. The GCI predicted with mesh A and mesh B is 0.273%. This is higher than the one calculated with mesh B and mesh C, which is 0.126%. The magnitude of the adiabatic efficiency error for mesh B is estimated to be 0.218%, which is sufficiently small for the purpose of this study. From this study, the spatial resolution of the intermediate mesh B is chosen for the simulations presented herein.

Figure 8(b) shows the overview of the circumferential recirculation channel (RC). This channel design broadly draws from a detail of a one-way valve by Nikola Tesla [12]. The recirculating flow channel shown in Fig. 8(b) is designed to suck air at the channel inlet and to re-inject it at the channel outlet into the main flow passage, to mitigate the reversed flow from the rotor tip clearance. The recirculating flow inside the RC is activated by the pressure difference between the channel inlet and the channel outlet. ANSYS ICEM CFD is used to generate the structured mesh for the recirculation channel. The number of nodes generated for the recirculation channel in Fig. 8(b) is 0.5 million. For the RC case simulations, this recirculation channel mesh is appended to the main passage mesh by defining the grid interface between these two meshes.

Table 1. Main design parameters of the NASA rotor 37.

		Design
Rotor total pressure ratio	-	2.106
Rotor polytropic efficiency	%	88.9
Number of the rotor blades	-	36
Rotational speed	rad s ⁻¹	-1800
Rotor inlet hub-to-tip diameter ratio	-	0.7
Blade aspect ratio	-	1.19
Tip relative inlet Mach number	-	1.4
Aerofoil profile		MCA

The flow analysis is conducted using both steady and time-dependent Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations. In this study, the realizable $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence closure model is used to estimate the eddy viscosity. Roe's flux difference splitting method is used, combined with the Roe approximate Riemann solver. For the convection term, a third-order MUSCL scheme provided by Van Leer [13] is used. For steady RANS simulations, the implicit integration method by Weiss et al. [14] is applied until a steady-state solution is reached. For time-dependent RANS simulations, a physical time discretization of second-order accuracy by Pandya et al. [15] is used. The physical time step is set to 4.8×10^{-6} seconds.

The total pressure P_{0in} and the total temperature T_{0in} at the computational domain inlet are specified as the international standard atmospheric condition at sea level. The turbulence intensity I and the turbulence length scale l at the computational domain inlet are specified based on the experimental test condition as reported in [9, 10]. The static pressure P_{out} at the computational domain outlet of Fig. 8 is set as ambient pressure to start with and then progressively increased, to simulate different rotor loading conditions. For steady RANS simulations, the static pressure is imposed under the condition of radial equilibrium. For time-dependent RANS simulations, a macroscopic pressure resistance model defined by Equation 1 is applied to the outlet boundary in order to allow the static pressure to change passage-to-passage during the stall inception. After obtaining numerically converged results at a back pressure of $P_{out} = 101.325$ kPa, using this result as the initial condition, the back pressure P_{out} is progressively increased up to the stall inception. The numerically converged operating point that has the lowest mass flow rate is defined as the operating limit of the rotor. To reduce the computational cost, a rotational periodic boundary condition is applied to both sides of the computational domain in the circumferential direction. The working fluid is assumed as dry air modelled as a compressible ideal gas. The specific heat capacity at constant pressure c_p is set to $1004 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The ratio of the specific heat capacities γ is set to 1.4 based on the literature [8]. Sutherland's viscosity law is used to estimate the molecular viscosity of the air.

$$P_{out} = P_{0in} + \frac{1}{2} c_t \bar{\rho} \bar{u}_a^2 \quad (1)$$

Validation of the numerical model

CFD predictions of radial profiles of circumferentially mass-averaged total pressure at Station 1 and at Station 4, tangential velocity at Station 4, and flow angle at Station 4 are shown in Fig. 9, for the benchmark simulation with no casing treatment. The radial profiles obtained by steady RANS simulations are shown in Fig. 9 by black solid lines. Figure 9 also show the radial profiles predicted by the unsteady RANS simulations by blue dotted lines.

For the time-dependent RANS simulations, the radial profiles are calculated by averaging four equispaced time points during one pitch blade rotation, at increments $\Delta t = 2\pi/(36 \times 5 \times \omega)$. There is no significant difference between corresponding predictions obtained by steady RANS and by time-dependent RANS. Overall, these predictions agree well with the corresponding experimental data reported by Dunham [9], and by Arima et al. [10]. The mass flow rate at the choked condition predicted by steady RANS is 20.82 kg s^{-1} , the one predicted by time-dependent RANS is 20.84 kg s^{-1} , both of which are sufficiently close to the measured mass flow rate of 20.93 kg s^{-1} for the purpose of this investigation. From these results, the current steady and time-dependent RANS simulations with the realizable $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence closure model are deemed to be capable of evaluating the performance of the NASA rotor 37.

Fig. 9. Comparison of rotor inflow and outflow mass-averaged radial profiles from CFD and experimental data reported by Dunham [9], and by Arima et al. [10].

Time dependent analysis of rotor tip stall

It is of interests to reproduce the salient flow stages leading to rotating stall in the axial rotor. Unsteady multi-passage RANS simulations are carried out for the NASA rotor 37 to clarify the rotor tip flow structures responsible for the rotating stall inception. Fig. 10(a) shows the time history of the mass flow rate \dot{m} calculated by Equation 2 and of the outlet static pressure P_{out} , during stall inception. From the operating limit predicted by converged time-dependent simulations, the pressure resistance coefficient c_t of Equation 2 is changed from $c_t = 0.88$ to $c_t = 0.92$ at $t_{rev} = 0.0$ revs. in Fig. 10(a).

$$\dot{m} = (\dot{m}_{in} + \dot{m}_{out})/2 \quad (2)$$

An initial slow mass flow reduction is followed by a sudden drop in the mass flow rate. To visualize how the flow structure develops in the compressor, axial flow velocity distributions at 0.85 blade span are shown in Fig. 10(b). In order to clarify the regions of backflow where the axial flow velocity $u_a < 0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, the $u_a = 0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ contour is set to border the blue and yellow areas. In the yellow areas, $u_a < 0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. At $t_{rev} = 0.0$ revs., there are no significant difference in the flow structure among the 12 blade passages. Low axial flow velocity regions due to the leading edge shockwave are captured in front of all the rotor blade leading edges. The periodicity of the flow structure among the rotor passages starts to collapse after the increase of back pressure at $t_{rev} = 0.0$ revs. At $t_{rev} = 8.0$ revs., the axial velocity distributions

show the development of low velocity regions in some rotor passages, as highlighted in Fig. 10(b). This low velocity region determines a flow blockage near the casing wall. This, in turn, causes the flow to spill over the rotor blade leading edge from one passage to the adjacent rotor passage, opposite to the blade rotation direction. This flow spillage, by increasing the local flow incidence angle, makes the adjacent rotor passage stall. By this, the flow disturbance propagates in the opposite direction to the blade rotation direction. The reduction in axial flow velocity grows as the physical time increases and then visible flow separation occurs on the suction surface of the rotor blade at $t_{rev} = 9.4$ revs. Eventually, this flow separation causes a large-scale breakdown of the flow structure through the rotor.

(a) Time history of mass flow rate and outlet static pressure during the stall inception.

(b) Axial velocity iso-color levels at the 0.85 blade span.

Fig. 10. Axial velocity distribution at 0.85 blade span, showing time-dependent evolution of tip stall.

Numerical evaluation of a passive flow control design for improving stall margin

Figure. 11 shows the effect of the RC shown in Fig. 8 on the overall compressor performance characteristics. The operating points of the baseline (BL) case and the recirculation channel case (RC) are obtained by time-dependent RANS simulations. Fig. 11(a) uses the same abscissa as Fig. 11(b). Fig. 11(b) uses the same legend as

Fig. 11(a). The choked mass flow rate \dot{m}_{choked} of the baseline case, with no casing treatment, is used to normalize the abscissa for all the simulations. The rotor adiabatic efficiency is calculated by Equation 3. Due to the computational cost, only the near-stall operating point is simulated by the multi-passagge computational domain, both in the BL case and in the RC case.

$$\eta = \left[\frac{(\bar{P}_{04}/\bar{P}_{01})^{(\kappa-1)/\kappa} - 1}{(\bar{T}_{04}/\bar{T}_{01}) - 1} \right] \times 100 \quad (3)$$

By the application of the recirculation channel, the operating range is extended to 0.827 of \dot{m}_{choked} . This provides a rotor stall margin (SM) improvement of 8.9% with respect to the baseline case. Herein, the rotor SM is calculated by Equation 4, which is given in [16].

$$SM = \left[1 - \frac{\dot{m}_{NS} \times (\bar{P}_{04}/\bar{P}_{01})_{PE}}{\dot{m}_{PE} \times (\bar{P}_{04}/\bar{P}_{01})_{NS}} \right] \times 100 \quad (4)$$

As shown in Fig. 11(b), this useful extension of the rotor operating range is achieved without the adiabatic efficiency penalty of other treatments, reported in [4, 5].

Fig. 11. Overall compressor performance characteristics showing the impact of the investigated recirculation channel casing treatment.

It is of interest to analyse the changes in the flow structure of the rotor passage. The near-casing flow pattern is illustrated in Fig. 12 by contours of specific entropy. These contours are shown on eight meridional planes for the baseline case, in Fig. 12(a), and for the recirculation channel case, in Fig. 12(b). These eight meridional planes are generated between two blades every 1.5 degrees in the

circumferential direction. The specific entropy s is calculated by:

$$s = c_p \ln \frac{T_0}{T_{0in}} - R \ln \frac{P_0}{P_{0in}} \quad (5)$$

where T_0 is the total temperature, P_0 is the total pressure, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, R is the specific gas constant, and the subscript in denotes the computational domain inlet.

Fig. 12. Specific entropy colour iso-levels on eight meridional planes showing the spread of specific entropy inside the main flow passage.

To highlight the interaction between the flow injection and the main passage flow, only the portion of the axial planes where the specific entropy is $\geq 0.05 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is shown. The specific entropy distributions inside the RC are not shown in these figures, to prevent graphical clutter, and the edges of the casing channel are displayed by white lines.

Both BL and RC models predict a high specific entropy region extending from the rotor tip towards the hub, as shown in Fig. 12(b), which is caused by the tip leakage vortex. In the baseline case of Fig. 12(a), the high specific entropy distribution extends up to the near the leading edge of the adjacent rotor blade. Fig. 12(a) and (c) highlights by red arrows that the distance between the rotor leading edge and this high specific entropy region is lengthened by applying the recirculation channel casing treatment. This is probably due to the flow injection from the recirculation channel outlet, which has the favourable effect of mitigating the reversed flow near the casing wall. This local suppression of the flow blockage may be the main reason of the improvement in the rotor stability observed in Fig. 11.

Due to the flow injection at the channel outlet, a localized high specific entropy region is predicted below the injection opening as highlighted in Fig. 12(c). Nevertheless, this flow injection contributes to reducing the specific entropy near the casing wall. This compensating effect may explain why a penalty in the adiabatic efficiency is not observed in Fig. 11(b) for the RC case.

CONCLUSION

Two design challenges for axial compressors related to their unsteady flow have been discussed in this paper. These are the periodic wake/boundary interaction and the stall inception in a highly loaded rotor.

Time-dependent measurements of the static pressure fluctuations over a flat plate elucidated the interaction between the flat plate boundary layer and an on-coming gust. These measurements, obtained by a microphone array, have shown that the inception of turbulent flow associated with a laminar separation bubble at around $x = 0.75 \text{ m}$ is calmed by the operation of three synthetic jets placed near the flat plate leading edge. The perturbed flow patch generated by these jets is broadly analogous to an oncoming wake, generated, for instance, from an upstream blade row. By this analogy, rather than being always detrimental to efficiency, wakes past blade rows can produce a calmed region, which reduces profile loss in turbomachines.

Time-dependent three-dimensional RANS numerical simulations of the NASA rotor 37 clarified the unsteady aerodynamic features responsible for rotating stall inception. A recirculation channel type casing treatment was tested numerically to mitigate rotor tip stall inception. The improvement in the stall margin from the baseline case predicted by time-dependent RANS simulations is 8.9%. The flow through the recirculation channel, activated by the pressure difference between the recirculation channel inlet

and outlet, is shown to keep the near-casing pressure side clear from high specific entropy for longer, delaying rotor tip stall inception.

The impact potential from this casing treatment is high. Future high speed jet aircraft stand to benefit from enhanced stall margin that this recirculation channel can confer. The greater all-attitude engine stability at no efficiency penalty this casing treatment can deliver enhances both the effectiveness and the safety of sorties, which is likely to be attractive to pilots, air staff, airframe and engine manufactures.

NOMENCLATURE

CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
GCI	Grid Convergence Index
MCA	Multiple-Circular-Aerofoil
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
T-S	Tollmien-Schlichting

Symbols

C_p	Pressure coefficient
c_p	Specific heat capacity at constant pressure
c_t	Pressure resistance coefficient
h_r	Radial height from the hub
H_r	Radial height from the hub to the casing
I	Turbulence intensity
k	Specific turbulent kinetic energy
L	Flat plate length
L_T	Transition length
l	Turbulence length scale
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate
P	Pressure
R	Specific gas constant of dry air
s	Specific entropy
T	Temperature
t_{rev}	Time in rotor revolutions
u_a	Axial velocity
u_t	Tangential velocity
β	Hartree parameter
γ	Intermittency
ε	Specific dissipation rate of specific turbulent kinetic energy
η	Adiabatic efficiency
κ	Specific heat ratio, 1.4
ρ	Density
ω	Rotational speed

Subscripts

0	Stagnation condition
1	Station 1
4	Station 4
in	Computational domain inlet
out	Computational domain outlet
ref	Reference

Superscripts

$\bar{}$	Mass-averaging
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REFERENCES

- [1] Gostelow, J.P., "Design and performance evaluation of four transonic compressor rotors," *Trans. ASME J. Eng. for Power*, Jan. 1971.
- [2] Cameron, J. D., Morris, S. C., Barrows, S. T., and Chen, J. P., "On the interpretation of casing measurements in axial compressors," *American Society of Mechanical Engineering, Paper GT2008-51371*, 2008.
- [3] Gallimore, S. J., Bolger, J. J., Cumpsty, N. A., Taylor, M. J., Wright, P. I. and Place, J. M. M., "The use of sweep and dihedral in multistage axial flow compressor blading – Part 1: University research and methods development," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 124, No. 4, 2002, pp. 521-532.
- [4] Gourdain, N. and Leboeuf, F., "Unsteady simulation of an axial compressor stage with casing and blade passive treatments," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 131, No. 2, 2009, pp. 021013-1-12.
- [5] Houghton, T., and Day, I., "Enhancing the stability of subsonic compressors using casing grooves," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 133, No. 2, 2010, pp. 021007-1-11.
- [6] Hathaway, M. D., "Self-recirculating casing treatment concept for enhanced compressor performance," *NASA Technical memorandum TM-2002-211569*, 2002.
- [7] Hartree, D. R., "On an equation occurring in Falkner and Skan's approximate treatment of the equations of the boundary layer," *Proc. Cambridge Phil. Soc.*, Vol. 33, No. 2, 1937, pp. 223-239.
- [8] Moore, R. D., and Reid, L., "Performance of single-stage axial-flow transonic compressor with rotor and stator aspect ratios of 1.19 and 1.26, respectively, and with design pressure ratio of 2.05," *NASA Technical paper TP1659*, 1980.
- [9] Dunham, J., "CFD validation for propulsion system components," *AGARD-AR-355*, May 1998.
- [10] Arima, T., Sonoda, T., Shirotori, M., Tamura, A., and Kikuchi, K., "A numerical investigation of transonic axial compressor rotor flow using a low-Reynolds-number $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 121, No. 1, 1999, pp. 44-58.
- [11] Roache, P. J., "Perspective: A method for uniform reporting of grid refinement studies," *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 116, No. 3, 1994, pp. 405-413.
- [12] Tesla, N., New York, NY, U.S. Patent Application for a "Valvular Conduit," 1329559, filed 2 February 1916.
- [13] Van Leer, B., Thomas, J. L., Roe, P. L. and Newsome, R. W., "A comparison of numerical flux formulas for the Euler and Navier-Stokes equations," *AIAA Paper 87-1104*, 1987.
- [14] Weiss, J. M., Maruszewski, J. P., and Smith, W. A., "Implicit solution of the Navier-Stokes equations on unstructured meshes," *AIAA Technical Paper AIAA-97-2103*, 1997.
- [15] Pandya, S. A., Venkateswaran, S., and Pulliam, T. H., "Choice of variables and preconditioning for time dependent problems," *AIAA Technical Report AIAA-2003-3692*, 2003.
- [16] Sakuma, Y., Watanabe, T., Himeno, T., Kato, D., Murooka, T., and Shuto, Y., "Numerical analysis of flow in a transonic compressor with a single circumferential casing groove: Influence of groove location and depth on flow instability," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 136, No. 3, 2013, pp. 031017-1-9.